

Migration Diaspora And Remittance Review

Volume: 4
Issue: 1
Year: 2024
ISSN: 2791-254X

Local Entrepreneurship Enhancing Socioeconomic Status: A Descriptive Study of Migrant Workers in Nepal

Chongbang Nirmal¹

Dr Nguyen Thi Do Quyen²

Aryal Bishnu³

Gautam Mohan³

¹Tribhuvan University, Nepal

²Faculty of Social Sciences and Humanities, Thang University, Vietnam.

³Independent researcher, Nepal

Corresponding Author: Chongbang Nirmal

Email: nirech2005@gmail.com

Abstract

Local products and enterprises are impacted owing to external product dominance. Changes in customer behavior, advertising dominance, and the cost-effectiveness of mass production retard the development of local markets for locally produced goods. These are substantial obstacles to local production and marketing. The study examined how resourceless households have battled with their products owing to competition from macro production industries at the local level, and how this has affected their daily lives and means of subsistence in the context of resourceless homes in Dang, Nepal. The research paper examined the existing local entrepreneurial environment and significant impediments for resourceless communities in the area of study. The research employed a descriptive methodology. Through a closed and open-ended questionnaire administered to local informants, primary data has been gathered. Landless, local entrepreneurship, and community-based activities on self-entrepreneurship related to published information were considered as a secondary source for this study. Analyzing quantitative data involved descriptive & case study involved in qualitative analysis. Local business is hindered by a small market, high transportation costs, weak market networking, expensive labor engagement in production (dominated by external manufacturing), and a lack of startup capital. The support of seed funding, the improvement of skills, the use of micromachines, and local promotional policies on the production and sale of local products may be able to increase the sustainability of local entrepreneurship.

Keywords

Accessibility, capital, entrepreneurship, seed-grant, resilience.

Migration Diaspora and Remittance Review

438-452

Copyright: © 2024 by the authors. Licensee KMF Publishers (www.kmf-publishers.com). This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Article reuse guidelines:

Open Access

<http://kmf-publishers.com/mdrr/>

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.>

Background

The community has been engaged in microeconomic strengthening through its local efforts. Vegetable farming, chicken rearing, goat rearing, pig farms, dairy products, and small businesses based on local resources are major local economic drivers. Due to the area's limited economic opportunities, many individuals of productive age are seeking new opportunities elsewhere. A large number of migrant workers had returned to their home countries, and they had established micro, small, and medium-sized businesses in the local environment. The World Health Organization declared COVID-19 a global pandemic on March 11, 2020 (Kenyon, 2020), but the global community continues to suffer, especially during socioeconomic recovery as a result of this pandemic. Although the pandemic and its macroeconomic effects have affected virtually every aspect of life, this report focuses primarily on the pandemic's profound effects on trade and development (DEVELOPMENT, 2020). This paper focuses on local entrepreneurs led by migrant workers and their families. How these enterprises were affected by external dominance, what the major challenges are, and how they can adapt to these external socioeconomic shocks are the main topics of study in this paper's field.

Due to limited market accessibility, lack of glitz, lack of publicity, limited manufacturing, a weak business network, intense competition from external products, and inadequate state socioeconomic support policies, it is difficult for local resource-based entrepreneurs to survive (Zhou & Wen, 2022). Due to the inherent economic fragility of the area under study, the problem of developing socioeconomic resilience is crucial for small businesses. The concept of economic resilience also clarifies how some economically vulnerable small businesses have been able to thrive despite their extreme susceptibility to external shocks. Consideration of resilience building also conveys that economically vulnerable communities should not be content with their vulnerability. Instead, they should adopt policies that strengthen their ability to withstand external shocks and receive robust support from the government and external agencies.

Competitiveness is a combination of competition and cooperation between businesses to foster innovation and generate net value added or other forms of monetary gain. The increasing prevalence of entrepreneurs and small businesses is one of the most noticeable aspects of the contemporary world. Men and women are increasingly rejecting the job security and other perks of corporate life in favour of the risks of entrepreneurship. Small businesses contribute positively to national economies by creating jobs, decentralising economic activities, reducing rural-to-urban migration, boosting economic viability, promoting income redistribution, and fostering entrepreneurship (Muzari, 2011).

Microbusinesses play an important role because they can help disadvantaged and vulnerable populations gain independence by providing employment opportunities. Researchers and policymakers should be aware of how microenterprises influence the various characteristics of the empowerment of poor and vulnerable people. By better understanding and implementing initiatives, the government and policymakers can help promote local microbusinesses, resulting in the overall empowerment of disadvantaged people. Jacob and Munuswamy (2022) argue that economic development cannot occur without the empowerment of women. Entrepreneurial skills, technical knowledge, skill training, and marketing skills should be taught to women so that they can launch a business

more successfully and sustainably. Local economic strikes have a significant negative impact on resource-based businesses, with negative effects ranging from household income to local development and affecting the socioeconomic domain.

The informal economy and small and medium-sized businesses are in a state of crisis as a result of prolonged economic slowdowns, poor mobility, and limited financial transaction opportunities. Farah N. Mawani et al. (2021) explain that COVID-19 is a global health issue with limited opportunities for migrant workers, their dependents, and the economy to develop concurrently under unforeseen conditions. This has wreaked havoc on rural communities' local production, self-reliance, and socioeconomic status. These crises are rapidly aggravating socioeconomic and health disparities, thereby contributing to economic instability in developing nations. The loss of local production results in constrained labour markets, which in turn leads to constrained production and the predominance of outsourced production, which has an impact on entrepreneurial and self-employment motivations. Local entrepreneurship is a key factor in the transformation of socioeconomic factors within a community. This is a significant driver of regional development. It promotes substantive innovation and self-entrepreneurship in the region, based on regional framework conditions and global demand. Wright, F., and Kelley, D. (2020) conclude that the government's response to the pandemic has been significantly more successful in restoring normalcy to local entrepreneurs. When government or external support agencies provide local entrepreneurs with financial assistance, their businesses are more likely to survive. Global market dominance creates socioeconomic vulnerabilities in local contexts that directly impact the private and SME environment, ultimately leading from entrepreneurship to the market, from the market to financial institutions, and from It has a direct impact on the debt cycle to local GDP, particularly for working people. domestic and international courses. Takahashi, N., and Guelich, U. (2020) define how the governments of Japan and Thailand sponsor entrepreneurs, implement enabling policies, enhance domestic market dynamics, foster the opening of local markets, and provide professional training for new entrepreneurs. Specify how the programme catered to their requirements. They attempt to convert these external stresses and shocks into employment opportunities.

Now is the time for a global collective commitment to combat economic instability, contribute to regional financial empowerment, advocate for financial order, and make modest economic contributions. Provide bank debt without control or on the basis of interest-free loans, via inter-entrepreneurial social support, social protection funds, and government revolving funds, in order to revitalise local entrepreneurship, contribute to the local economy, and contribute to the global economy. maintain economic and social order. Already, migrant workers and their families struggle for a better socioeconomic standing. Numerous nations endeavoured to find more sustainable economic destinations and improved means of prosperity. Recent pandemic has exacerbated the socioeconomic struggle of the developing world.

Diego D'Adda et al. (2020) describe the dramatic economic shifts that influence the behaviour of the poor and economically disadvantaged as well as public institutions. Lockdowns reflect the primary negative role of socioeconomic impacts, decreased savings, and ongoing investment. Local entrepreneurs rely on government assistance and stimuli for a speedy local economic recovery. Several of the state's stimulus packages and policies

have made it simpler for business owners to take a breather and attempt to recover from their businesses. Sayono et al. (2018) assert that the economic history of South Malang residents changed from a plantation economy and subsistence agriculture to a capitalist economy between 1980 and 2015. This shift has occurred historically for a number of reasons. The first consists of internal and external factors. Access to limited transportation, employment opportunities, education, and health care are domestic factors. External factors include the oil boom and the Asian miracle. As a result of, there are high-paying employment opportunities. Due to the mountainous and rocky terrain, environmental conditions are difficult and expensive to manage, and there are few natural resources that can be exploited for economic purposes.

A third reason is the sociocultural background of residents, who have been familiar with capitalist economics and monetization since colonial times. Instead of focusing on agriculture, they would prefer to live in their hometowns, establish plantations, and work abroad as a result of this shift in society's view of capital and money. In both developing and developed economies in the twenty-first century, the growing popularity of entrepreneurs and small businesses is one of the most noticeable trends.

Returning migrant workers are increasingly forgoing job security and other perks of corporate life in favour of the risks associated with entrepreneurship. Muzari (2021) claim the positive function of small businesses is gaining recognition in both developing and developed nations. The author also emphasised the significance of small businesses in promoting the decentralisation of economic activities because they are less location-sensitive than large corporations. Additionally, small businesses contribute to the mobilization of personal savings and expansion of entrepreneurship. Small businesses can also access the modest savings of owners who do not use the banking system and instead reinvest in their own businesses. Social institutions-based capital, local professional-based safety nets, and government social protection policies can all play a significant role in reviving entrepreneurship (Chongbang, 2021). Entrepreneurship is the aggregate action of social capital, social security, and strategic policy management. These characteristics can contribute to the formation of local social capital and the expansion of market-based entrepreneurship enablement.

The majority of returnee migrant workers have recently attempted to establish their own businesses, safeguard recent employment, and engage in stable enterprises with their workers. They are attempting to coordinate their entrepreneurship and community capital investments. The trend appears to be predominantly sustainable and resilient entrepreneurship. We must concentrate on gathering information on local assets, local and social support practises, and local social protection policy. Which can envision entrepreneurial development linkages in a variety of contexts. The impact on the underlying causes of socioeconomic inequalities, low supporting mechanisms, weak locally available social assets, and fewer social support practises can have a lasting effect on the development of entrepreneurship.

Theoretical Framework

This study is primarily based on conservation of dependency theory: world system theory. The stages of economic growth will not occur because the least developed nations are trapped in oppressive interactions with more developed nations. This has led to the concept of a worldwide division of labour, with unskilled labourers in the core countries and unskilled labourers in the periphery. Due to limited employment opportunities in their home countries, highly skilled workers in the periphery may be encouraged to migrate to the core countries (a phenomenon known as brain drain).

Duality has an impact on the subnational level as a result of dependence theory. Dualism, which is influenced by notions of dependence, refers to situations in which two areas interact and one area advances at the expense of the other. This concept can be examined at various scales, including global (as with dependency theory), regional (within a country), and urban/rural.

In response to modernization theory, a new set of development concepts emerged in the 1950s that emphasised structure or the global context in which countries operated, according to Moseley (2017). Dependency theory is an example of this new type of structuralist thought. This emphasis on structure meant that international relations were at least as important as domestic policies in determining a country's future development. Frank (1974) argued that the economies of the tropics (Africa, Latin America, and Asia) were fundamentally "underdeveloped" during the colonial era, as European powers reshaped these economies for their own benefit (by a combination of taxing policies and coercion). Frank asserts that in exchange for wealth and power, developing-country elites frequently collaborated with colonists to manage primary extraction. Farmers in tropical nations were frequently persuaded or compelled to cultivate commodity crops for the develop nations market (sometimes at the expense of subsistence agriculture) and/or compelled to abandon their own farms in order to work for wages on vast plantations or in developing nations.

Internationally, the dependency theory has resulted in significant policy modifications in developing nations. Import substitution was based on the notion that finished goods must be produced domestically and not imported from core countries. Faced with intense competition from companies, the governments of neighbouring nations frequently participated directly in the establishment of such companies. These government-owned businesses became known as Parastatals. In addition, governments typically erect tariff barriers to safeguard such emerging or nascent industries until they are able to withstand international competition. It was argued that foreign companies operating in these industries would not do so in the best interests of the local population and development. It could lead to economic growth, but the problem was that the majority of profits were sent back home. Theoretically, by acquiring such industries (and operating them as quasi-national enterprises), the nation could ensure that the profits from these mines are reinvested in the development of other industries.

The external economic force had an impact not only on socioeconomic transformation, but also on the education system, the planning procedure, and long-term human resource development. A migrant worker has engaged in a variety of domestic and international employment arrangements. In this context, they have returned from abroad

and are engaged in self-employment. Due to increased external market and value chain influence, they are struggling to maintain their trade. Since they rely on external materials, connections, and market drivers, returnee migrant workers have not yet established themselves as expected on the local socioeconomic market.

Methodology

This study was conducted in 2022 in Dang, Nepal, as part of a returnee migrant worker status study. The study was based on the collection of primary data regarding the status of returnee workers and their status as entrepreneurs in Dang. This study is predominantly quantitative with some qualitative description. For sample collection, we used convenience sampling. All responses were gathered via a closed/open-ended questionnaire with the assistance of front-line workers from various projects, and telephonic opinion collection was utilised for data triangulation.

The independent variables are skill empowerment of local entrepreneurs, market strengthening, network building, changing needs and market linkages, and external domination of the market impacted local economic enhancement capacity of returnee migrant worker household capacity into entrepreneurship enhancement in the study area. The dependent variable (local economic enhancement capacity of returnee migrant workers) is based on the independent variables B1 (Skill empowerment), B2 (Market strengthening), and B3 (Returnee migrant workers' local economic enhancement capacity) (Networking building). B4 (Changing need and market linkage) and B5 (External domination). The result is that the effect of framing on returnee migrant worker entrepreneurship is 8.44 times greater than that of independent variables on a dependent variable. On the basis of returnee migrant workers and their dependents who engage in self-employment, the sample size for the survey was set at approximately 62 households.

Result and discussion

Descriptive Analysis

Mean	36.6
Standard Error	8.078366
Median	39
Mode	18
Standard Deviation	18.06378
Sample Variance	326.3
Kurtosis	-2.9943
Skewness	-0.15661
Range	37
Minimum	18
Maximum	55
Sum	183
Count	5
Confidence Level (95.0%)	22.42914

Nearly 16,000 Nepalis migrate to the Gulf States for temporary work, with thousands more going to other Middle Eastern nations (Migrant Workers' Access to Justice at Home: Nepal, 2014). The economic growth and impact of the regular shocks such as pandemics, unemployment and much more are seeming to be an interrelated phenomenon. Impact of external factors, domination of corporate production and minor products related phenomenon are highly remarkable while returnee migrant workers are engaged into self-enterprises.

Much attention has been focused on the exploitation of low-wage migrant laborer in the Middle East, where harm is common and severe, and access to justice is limited. However, the story of labor migration begins and ends at home. Migrant workers are frequently confronted with a variety of abuses during their recruitment in Nepal and making them more vulnerable to exploitation overseas ahead. Among of the respondents families, 6.45% said returnee workers has back from Qatar, 9.68% back from Kuwait, 1.61% back from Japan, 3.23% back from Portugal, 1.61% back from Bahrain, 32.26% back from India, 4.84% come back from Malaysia, 30.65% are back from Dubai, 1.61% are from European countries, 6.45% back from Saudi Arab, and 1.62% are back from other countries.

In the study area, mainly 41.94% of respondents said household-based entrepreneurship has contributed to the capital formulation, among of them 32.26% are engaged in self-entrepreneurship, 32.26% said it is supporting factors on capital formulation locally. 29.03% of respondents said the local self-skill-based entrepreneurship can make differences into self-sustaining approaches, 11.29% said their income is sufficient into home operation, and only 16.13% of respondents said the additional saving can be manage through their entrepreneurship.

Based on the above discussion, most of the returnee migrant workers and their dependents trying to start up their entrepreneurs locally. They have tried to set up based on their efforts, some of them got external support from their relatives and local micro cooperatives but still support gaps from state recognition and support. Most of the local entrepreneurs are expecting on supportive engagement on socioeconomic recovery from local financial institutions and the government. While entrepreneurs were trying to retain and revive their services based on their own capital, which is not sufficient. Some of the development project and financial institutions are supported by their initiations to establish of returnee migrant worker entrepreneurship. The local financial intuitions (cooperatives) are considered as a local support unit on financial assistance, which is based on daily and monthly based saving from among of members in local entrepreneurships. 54% of responders are said they are getting some financial loan from local cooperatives on their entrepreneurship start-up.

During the FGD events at study area Maya Chaudhary, Vima B.K, Goma Oli, Bhabana Oli, Mandakini Khadka, and Mankaji Budhamgar has shared their own entrepreneurship story with data collection team. They explained further as follows:

The dream of Maya is to return the husband from foreign employment

Maya Chaudhary lives in Ghorahi Sub-metropolitan city ward no.-2, Dang. She has 1 son and her husband went to Saudi Arabia for foreign employment. After her husband went to Saudi, she was busy working at home and she was totally dependent on remittances sent by her husband.

One thing comes to her mind, instead of sitting idle; she could do something that would earn her some income. Therefore, she planned to start a grocery shop that covers small areas of her village. She took Rs. 1,50,000 as a loan from microfinance and started local production and imported material-based grocery shops. In the beginning, it was a normal selling but now everyone around her village comes to her shop to buy the goods. Her daily selling is approximately Rs. 3000 to 4000 and net income is Rs.500 to 600 per day.

She has also skilled of sewing and cutting, she sews cloths in free time while sitting on shop which creates extra income. In this way, with the income from the shop and tailoring, she is also paying the loan and also saving 500 per day. She says, "We don't need to foreign employment to earn money, so I am thinking of calling my husband to Nepal soon.

Became entrepreneur with little money

Vima B.K., permanent resident of Ghorahi Sub-metropolitan city, ward no.-2, Dang. Her husband went to foreign employment in Qatar. She has been living with one daughter and son as a joint family. After her husband went to Qatar, she had taken care of the children and the house. She maintained the house from the remittance sent by her husband. Vima, who did not about business, felt that require a lot of money to start a business.

When she participated in the financial literacy class conducted by the Ghorahi Municipality, where she can understand how to start a business? She thought, if the local goat farming could start, the money sent by her husband would be saved. Then, she started goat farming with 10 goats.

She says that it was difficult because of a lack of technical knowledge at the initial stage. But now she consults with the municipal veterinary officer if any problem appeared. At present, she has 15 goats of the locally advanced breed. Now, she saves Rs. 2200 per month in cooperatives and microfinance institutions through goat rearing. If there is support from the municipality, she aims to add some more goats and bring her husband back from foreign employment. She says, "Local entrepreneurship is not a big thing. If you have a desire from your heart, you can become an entrepreneur even with little money."

Financial Literacy Class Made Entrepreneurs

Goma Oli, 25 years old, living in Lamahi Municipality Ward No. 3 Narayanpur, Dang, is a housewife from a normal family. She has a family of 4 people in her house. Her husband has been working abroad for the past 5 years, 4 years in Dubai and currently living in Saudi Arabia. All household expenses of her family of 4 depended on remittance sent by her husband. Apart from foreign employment, there were no other sources of income. She had no savings as all the money was spent on household expenses. She was worried because there was no financial progress along with the pain of being away from her husband for a long time. She was thinking that her husband's income would be saved if she could only earn for the household expenses. But she had no idea what to do. At the same time, she got information about participating in a financial literacy class through a local government representative of Lamahi Municipality. The class, which is conducted for 21 weeks, is discussed in various sessions. From poverty to prosperity, after discussing the session, she thinks of becoming an entrepreneur. But not only to become an entrepreneur, has it also required skill training and experience. For that financial literacy facilitator facilitate her all the necessary things to become an entrepreneur.

Goma thinks to start poultry form but she didn't have money to build coop. So she told her husband about her business plan and all things which learn in financial literacy class. Then her husband sent her NPR. 100000/-. In the beginning, coop was made to hold 200 chicks. For the first time, she started poultry farming with 200 chicks, but it did not go as she expected. In the first lot she had lost 20000/- due to the lack of knowledge on poultry farming. But she didn't give up and said that when a challenge comes in business, you have to face it and move forward. This is possible only when all family members supportive and her husband always encouraged her.

Then again, she kept 200 chicks. This time, she makes a profit by covering up for the first time's loss. Now Goma is very happy after gradually increasing profits. Goma says that earlier the money sent by her husband from abroad could only be spent on household expenses and children's education, but now more than half of the money is saved. Now is a support for the future, said monthly Rs. 1200| -She started saving, when asked why she didn't find a source of income and didn't save until now, she said what would happen from normal agricultural animal husbandry and if her husband sent 40,000 abroad it would not be enough, she was thinking what would happen with normal animal and bird rearing here. There was an opportunity to learn many things from financial literacy and psychosocial counseling classes.

Goma says that today we can eat fresh food from home and it has become easy to manage household expenses, now we have to gradually increase poultry and goat farming and tell her husband to return to Nepal and do self-employment at home. She says that she is thinking of becoming more self-employed.

Bhawana is happy after finding a way to earn

32 years old Bhabana Oli who lives in Babai Rural Municipality, Dang. She is a housewife and she has 3 family members including 7 years daughter and 34 years husband. Her husband Nar Bahadur Roka Magar has been working in Saudi Arabia for the past 10 years and his monthly earnings is NPR. 50000/- . Bhabana's source of income was foreign employment or he had to depend on remittance. She wanted to do some business on her own. But she had no experience on about these things.

In the same time, when she participated in the entrepreneurship development training under the MEDPA program in Babai Rural Municipality while discussing about how to start business and how to become entrepreneur in different sessions. She had learned about keeping income and expenses, saving daily and monthly, planning expenses, investing in productive areas, etc. Her desire to become an entrepreneur and earn income grew. Then, she has consulted with her husband and took loan NPR. 100000/- from cooperative and withdraw her saving NPR. 200000/- which send her husband from abroad. And, Bhabana has started grocery shop in the village.

Bhabana feels like she has found a way to earn money. The income from the grocery store has covered the household expenses and the child's education expenses. Bhabana says that now she is making a net profit of 15 to 20 thousand monthly. She has managed to save 6 to 8 thousand monthly in the cooperative and she plans to expand her grocery store by investing more and accordingly, she is also trying to increase her income. She has paid off the loan of the cooperative.

In November 2022, Bhabana's husband Nar Bahadur returned home from Saudi Arabia after not going for foreign employment. As the wife earns by becoming a businessman, the husband is also involved in the same work. Bhabana is preparing to earn income together without sending her husband abroad. Accordingly, her husband is also happily helping Bhabana in the grocery store.

Bhabana's husband Nar Bahadur also says that he does not go again in foreign employment and lives happily with his wife and children. He wants to further expand and organize the business started by his wife. After joining the entrepreneurship development training conducted by Babai Rural Municipality, he is very impressed by seeing the changed daily life, thoughts, feelings and way of working.

A big achievement given by a small thought of Mandakini

Mandakini Khadka, who lives in Tulsipur sub-metropolitan City, ward no-5, Dang is a good housewife. She has 2 sons, elder son 21 years old who study in class 12 and younger son 15 years who study in class 9 near the village. In 2016, her husband went to Malaysia for employment due to the debt burden and low employment opportunities in Nepal. Since her husband went to Malaysia, her source of income was foreign employment; all things were depended in the remittance. Even after 7 years, the fact that she

had to rely on remittances to support the household expenses and that she had to stay away from her husband all the time was still bothering her. But she had no idea what to do next.

One day, she got a chance to participate in a financial literacy class conducted by the municipality where how to become an entrepreneur was being discussed. After that she consulted her husband and she thinks becoming an entrepreneur. But she had neither the skills nor the experience. That's why she thought of getting training related to sewing, for which her husband sent money from Malaysia and she took 3 months of training. Training and desire is not enough for becoming entrepreneur the main thing is that money needed. So, she consulted her husband and her husband also liked her plan then he was ready to invest to start her business. She has started her business from Rs.50000/- which was sending from her husband with two sewing machines.

In the initial days, her trailer was not functioning well due to lack of business knowledge, lack of market assessment and other external factors. At the same time, she got the opportunity to take entrepreneurship development training conducted by the municipality so that she could learn the challenges that may come in doing business and how to solve them and try to improve her business. Now she bought 2 more machines in NPR. 18000/- for tailoring at home. Everyone in the village takes her to her tailor because she is a good seamstress from which she earns 10 to 12000/- per month. So that she doesn't have to rely on your husband's money to run the household expenses.

Now her husband has come home on vacation and is very happy to see his wife's work. After saving some money, he is also thinking of returning to Nepal and becoming an entrepreneur. And Mandakini is also planning to conduct sewing and cutting training for others while expanding her business.

Mankaji's heart rejoiced in the 'Little Forest'

Mankaji Budhamgar of Dang-Ghorahi had a dream of becoming 'Lahure' in his mind right from his childhood until he was studying in class 12. But the dream of becoming a 'Lahure' from childhood changed with time. After finishing 12th grade, he also planned to go to America through illegal means like his other colleagues. But it is a dream, where do all dreams come true? After all his dreams were not fulfilled, he went to Korea for 5 years. It was not easy to go to Korea. He had to wait 2 years after passing the language. He had to face a lot of stress during that time. He felt that there was a difference between thinking about Korea and living in Nepal and experiencing it there. There were only two Nepalis in the company. There was no limit on working hours, but the salary was based on the basic set by the Korean government. In other companies, while working for the same amount, the salary of others was around 2 lakhs per month. But he barely had one lakh rupees. After working for one year, he changed the company with the consent of the company. In the changed company, the work was miserable, but the salary also came according to the hard work.

He also knew that employment in Korea is not permanent and the earnings here do not last a lifetime. Then Mankaji decided to do something in the country. Wife Preksha also supported Mankaji's decision. After completing the five-year contract, Mankaji was preparing to return home. He submitted his resignation to the company and started the process of immigration. As the immigration process was delayed by one day, the flight to Nepal left two days ago. After that, Nepal banned international flights to prevent the corona epidemic. Mankaji stayed in Korea for about four months. After waiting for almost four months, the government operated a rescue flight to bring Nepali people stuck abroad. Mankaji returned to Nepal through the first flight. Mankaji and Praeksha had the idea of doing something new. The ability to do this was given by the skill while preparing for Australia, Preksha also did an internship in Himalayan Java. She learned coffee and bakery skills from there, so they both decided to use those skills.

The anxiety was in its place, but support is a big thing, I got the support of my wife and family' Mankaji says with a smile, 'Even if I didn't go to Korea and she wasn't with me, it wouldn't have been possible. It is not that there are no cafes and bakeries in Ghorahi. There are also many sellers of coffee and bakery dishes. But proving our identity in many of them was very challenging. But they also passed to that challenge.

He looked for a place to open a cafe in Ghorahi. Mankaji built the structure of the cafe when there was a lockdown in the country to prevent corona infection. About 6.5 million investments was required to prepare the structure of the cafe, the coffee machine, etc. Sadu Dai (wife's cousin) also invested half in the cafe. He named it 'Little Forest'.

Bakery and coffee are the specialties of this cafe. Whether you're going alone or with your family, you won't have any regrets after reaching the cafe. The atmosphere is calm. Different kinds of lights and flowers make sitting and eating in the cafe more enjoyable. The seating table and other decorations are captured by everyone who goes there on their mobile phones. There is also an arrangement to take photos of customers who come to the cafe. For those who come to celebrate their special day including birthdays, there are decorations accordingly. Then overall little Forest gives a glimpse of Korean cafes. "It has been better than expected in a short time, when we started, we thought that we would not have to pay house rent and staff expenses from our own pockets," says Mankaji in a satisfied pose, "The business that has happened now has made it look like it was very small." Now Mankaji has employed 11 people in the cafe. Mankaji and his wife Preksha also work from morning to evening. When I reach home after cleaning in the evening, sometimes it is 12 midnight.

Mankaji remember Korea when he goes to work morning, noon and night. In Korea, owner also worked with the workers. At that time, Mankaji thought - why did he work even as an owner? Now when he works as an owner himself, Mankaji feels - work is work.

He says that he has not calculated the profit and loss as he has just started the work. But he says that the current earnings are more than expected. Sometimes there is no seating in the cafe due to the customer crowd. When people return without finding a place to stay, they feel sad. So now he plans to increase the space and make the cafe even bigger.

After living in Korea for 5 years and seeing the tendency to return to Nepal after returning to Nepal, Mankaji thinks that everyone should use the money earned by hard work abroad in the right place. He thinks it is better to be happy with his people in the country than to suffer the stress of working abroad away from his country and family.

Economic growth is also influenced by external factors. Because of informal control over education, knowledge production and management, employment generation, and management, so-called poor and underdeveloped countries are engaged in oppressive interactions with more developed countries. This has given rise to the concept of a global layer of human growth and development, nurturing and empowerment, budgeting and nutrition, skill transfer with labor, and the working force always laborer working as a periphery or under of skilled laborer in the core countries. As a result of this knowledge management and division, highly skilled workers in the periphery may be encouraged to migrate to the core countries for high pay with a high standard of living narratives. They always prefer migrants for new opportunities from their original space due to limited employment opportunities.

The dependency concept has resulted in some significant policy influences on developing communities based on a comparison of local findings from the studied area. Because of the lower local production assets, some local production is also based on imported raw materials, and skilled human resources are already assigned to the migrant worker for better financial return, and most of the local need commodities are dominated by external production, demonstrating how significantly the dependency theory is working here. Most enterprise production dominates socio-economic needs in the local environment, and mass production and declining production rates of enterprise commodities make local commodity-based production unable to compete with corporate production. And finally, local entrepreneurs are forced out of the local environment. The closure of local entrepreneurship is not only the closure of local production, but also has a multiplier effect on production, breaks the socio-economic chain, and ultimately breaks the chain of dependence to a high extent, adversely affecting the economy. With external economic compulsion, it affected not only the socioeconomic transformation but also the local educational environment, human settlement, long-term human resource development, and migration. This can affect settlement planning and imbalances in the urban environment, manufacturing, economy and national development.

External factors also influence economic growth. As a result of informal control over education, knowledge production and management, employment generation, and management, so-called poor and underdeveloped nations engage in oppressive interactions with more developed nations. This has led to the concept of a global layer of human growth and development, nurturing and empowerment, budgeting and nutrition, skill transfer with labor, and the working force always consisting of unskilled laborers in the core nations. Due to this knowledge management and division, highly skilled workers in the periphery may be encouraged to migrate to the core countries in search

of high wages and a high standard of living. Due to limited employment opportunities in their home region, they always favor immigrants for new opportunities.

Moseley (2017) offers his perspective on modernization theory. Due to the author's emphasis on structure, interactions between countries and the periphery were of equal importance. Not only do the core countries collect natural raw materials, but they also collect trained and semi-skilled human resources from the so-called developing world, thereby enhancing their economic prospects. They are utilizing their educational system, agricultural practices, and indigenous traditions for their own advancement. This immediately contributes to a more hospitable environment for voluntary migration, whether for additional education or to increase their earnings outside their home countries.

Frank (1974) asserts that in exchange for wealth and power, elites from developing nations frequently collaborated with colonists to oversee primary extraction. According to the author, farmers in tropical nations are routinely persuaded or compelled to plant commodity crops in response to market demand in developed nations.

A comparison of local findings from the area under study reveals that the concept of dependency has had significant policy implications for developing communities. Due to the lower local production assets, some local production is also based on imported raw materials, skilled human resources are already assigned to migrant workers for a better financial return, and the majority of local need commodities are dominated by external production, demonstrating how effectively the dependency theory is operating here. Local commodity-based production is unable to compete with enterprise production due to mass production and declining production rates of enterprise commodities. And finally, local entrepreneurs are compelled to leave the area. The end of local entrepreneurship not only results in the end of local production, but also has a multiplier effect on production, breaks the socio-economic chain, and to a large extent, breaks the chain of dependence, which has a negative impact on the economy. It affected not only the socioeconomic transformation but also the local educational environment, human settlement, long-term human resource development, and migration due to external economic pressure. This can influence urban planning, environmental imbalances, manufacturing, the economy, and national development.

Conclusion

It appears that external factors have a significant impact on economic growth in the study area. Particularly in the areas of empowerment, employment, and resource management. External factors exert a repressive influence on local entrepreneurs. Therefore, highly skilled human resources are employed as external workers in developed cities and are eager to migrate to core nations. Financial dependency affects local entrepreneurial management. Due to a lack of local production assets, most of the local production is reliant on imported raw materials, skilled human resources are already assigned abroad, and most local commodities are dominated by external sellers, demonstrating how strongly the dependency theory is at work here. Due to the lower status of skill empowerment, the weak market strengthening of local production, light and nonstrategic networking, the unwillingness to reform the market in response to current demands, and the high dominance of external products are significant impediments to the development of local entrepreneurship.

References

- Chongbang, N. (2021). Microeconomic Resilience Practices in Entrepreneurship during Pandemic: A Study of Pokhara, Nepal. *Journal of Pandemic Disaster and Recession*, 1(1), 51-62. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5771366>
- DEVELOPMENT, U. N. (2020). Impact of the Covid-19 Pandemic on Trade and Development. United Nations Publications. Retrieved from <https://shop.un.org>
- DeLongis, A., & Holtzman, S. (2005). Coping in context: the role of stress, social support, and personality in coping. *Journal of personality*, 73(6), 1633–1656. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-6494.2005.00361.x>
- Diego D’Adda, I. d. (2020). COVID-19 Impacts on Entrepreneurship: Italy and Spain. Diagnosing COVID-19 Impacts on Entrepreneurship. Retrieved from <https://www.gemconsortium.org/reports/covid-impact-report>
- Farah N. M. (2021). COVID-19 Economic Response and Recovery: A Rapid Scoping Review. *International Journal of Health Services*, 51(2), 247–260. doi:DOI: 10.1177/00207314211002785
- Frank, A. G. (1974). Dependence Is Dead, Long Live Dependence and the Class Struggle: An Answer to Critics. *Latin American Perspectives*, 1(1), 87–106. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/2633531>
- Kenyon, C. (2020). Flattening-the-curve associated with reduced COVID-19 case fatality rates- an ecological analysis of 65 countries. *Journal of Infection*, 98-99. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jinf.2020.04.007>
- Moseley, W. G. (2017). Dependency Theory. *International Encyclopedia of Geography: People, the Earth, Environment and Technology*, 1–5. doi:10.1002/9781118786352.wbieg1086 10.1002/9781118786352.wbieg1086
- Muzari, W.M. (2021). SMALL ENTERPRISE DEVELOPMENT. ASARE Publishers.
- Sayono, J., Utami, I. W. P., & Ayundasari, L. (2018). Migrant workers and socio-economic changes. *Masyarakat, Kebudayaan Dan Politik*, 31(2), 176–189. <https://doi.org/10.20473/mkp.V31i22018.176-189>
- Takahashi, U. G. (2020). COVID-19 Impacts on Entrepreneurship: Japan and Thailand. Diagnosing COVID-19 Impacts on Entrepreneurship. Retrieved from <https://www.gemconsortium.org/reports/covid-impact-report>
- Wright, D. K. (2020). COVID-19 Impacts on Entrepreneurship: United States. Global Entrepreneurship Research Association. Retrieved from <http://www.witchwoodhouse.com>
- Zhou, D., & Wen, X. (2022). Self-employment and health inequality of migrant workers. *BMC Health Serv Res* 22, 937. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-022-08340-4>